

Flavonoids from *Medicago polymorpha* Roxb.

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Manuscript received 15 September 1988, accepted 31 March 1989

In a previous communications^{1,2}, we reported the occurrence of a new sterol, two rare amides, aurantiamide acetate and auranamide and a 5-hydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxyflavone (1a) in the whole plant of *Medicago polymorpha* Roxb. (Fam.: Leguminosae). We now report the isolation and characterisation of three more 5-hydroxyflavone derivatives from the benzene extract of this plant.

The benzene extract of the defatted whole plant of *M. polymorpha* on chromatography over silica gel afforded a yellow crystalline solid from the benzene eluates, m.p. 222–24°, C₁₇H₁₄O₆ (M⁺ 314); λ_{max} (EtOH) 242, 248, 254, 260 and 337 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3330 and 1620 cm⁻¹; gave positive Shinoda test. It was characterised as 5,4'-dihydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflavone (1b) on the basis of its spectral analysis³.

The benzene-ethyl acetate (9:1) eluates obtained from the same chromatogram afforded successively two compounds, MP-2 and MP-3.

- 1a; R₁=R₂=OCH₃, R₃=H
 1b; R₁=R₂=OCH₃, R₃=OH
 1c; R₁=OCH₃, R₂=H, R₃=OH
 1d; R₁=R₂=OH, R₃=H

The compound MP-2, m.p. 285–86°, C₁₆H₁₂O₆ (M⁺ 284); λ_{max} (EtOH) 262 and 358 nm, gave positive Shinoda test. Its uv, ir, pmr and particularly the mass spectral data compared fairly well with those reported⁴ for 5,4'-dihydroxy-7-methoxyflavone (1c). The compound MP-3, m.p. 327–29°, C₁₅H₁₀O₆ (M⁺ 270) gave positive Shinoda test. It was identified as apigenin (1d) by its spectral analysis and comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc, co-ir and pmr spectral data) with an authentic sample.

Although the genus *Medicago* is a rich source of isoflavonoid class of compounds⁵, the occurrence of 5-hydroxyflavone derivatives in this species is being reported for the first time.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (R.P.).

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Extractives of *Sequoiadendron giganteum*

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Manuscript received 11 October 1988, revised 24 January 1989,
accepted 31 March 1989

OUR interest in the isolation of natural products having potential anticancer activity, led us to reinvestigate the leaves of *S. giganteum* which belongs to the family Taxidiaceae, a rich source of lignans of podophylloxin type. Podophylloxin is an active anticancer agent^{1,2}. Previous work on this plant resulted in the isolation of biflavonoids³ and sequirenes (norlignans)⁴. Material used in the present investigation was collected from the higher region of Kashmir and identified at Botany Department, University of Kashmir, Srinagar. Air-dried needles (5 kg) were extracted with petroleum ether and the concentrated extract was chromatographed on a column of silica gel to yield 1, m.p. 145–46° (eluted with benzene) and 2, m.p. 153–55° (with benzene-ethyl acetate, 9:1). The defatted plant material was then extracted exhaustively with ethanol which was concentrated and chromatographed on a column of silica gel. Benzene-ethyl acetate (4:1) eluate gave 3 which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 310°.

Savinin (1) had λ_{max} (MeOH) 237, 293 and 334 nm and ν_{max} 1735, 1640 and 1600 cm⁻¹. Pmr spectrum of 1 showed two 2H singlets at δ 5.95 and 6.00 attributable to methylenedioxy functions. AB part of an ABX system was discernible at δ 2.8, all eight lines being well-resolved (J_{AB} 17 Hz, J_{AX} 10 Hz and J_{BX} 4 Hz) and the X part as a broad multiplet at δ 3.75. A 2H doublet appeared further downfield at δ 4.28 (J 5 Hz). It was identified on the basis of m.p. 145–46° (lit.⁵ 146°) and spectral data as savinin. Stigmast-22-enol was identified on the basis of physical⁶ and spectral data (ir, pmr and mass). 3 gave a positive test with FeCl₃. It formed acetyl and methyl ether derivatives whose pmr analysis followed by a direct comparison of 3

with an authentic sample of bilobetin⁷⁻⁹ (m.m.p., co-tlc and ir) revealed its identity.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship to one of the authors (B.I.F.) and a Research Associateship to the other (S. A. K.), and to Prof. W. Rahman for authentic sample.

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Norditerpene Dilactones, Macrophylllic Acid and Biflavones from *Podocarpus latifolius*

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Manuscript received 26 October 1988, revised 16 March 1989,
accepted 31 April 1989

BIFLAVONES¹ and norditerpene dilactones² are taxonomically associated with the genus *Podocarpus* (*Podocarpaceae*), of which norditerpene dilactones possess pronounced biological activities³. We report here the result of our investigations on *Podocarpus latifolius*.

Material used in this investigation were collected from Forest Research Institute, Dehradun, where a voucher specimen has been deposited. Air-dried stem wood (5 kg) of *P. latifolius* was extracted with acetone. The acetone extract was concentrated and chromatographed on silica gel and eluted with benzene-ethyl acetate mixtures of increasing polarity. Elution with benzene yielded a homogeneous solid which was crystallised as colourless needles from methanol, m.p. 135°; it gave a positive Liebermann-Burchard test and was identified as β -sitosterol (1). Elution with benzene-ethyl acetate (17:3) afforded another solid (2) which was

Crystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture, m.p. 235-36°. Uv spectral data indicated 2 to be aromatic and ir spectral data, indicated it to be an acid. Further, pmr spectral data showed the presence of two isopropyl and four tertiary methyl groups in 2. These facts taken together with the mass spectral data in which M^{+} appeared at m/z 630 corresponding to the composition of $C_{40}H_{54}O_6$, led to the identification of 2 as macrophylllic acid⁴. Elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (4:1) yielded a solid 3 which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 310-12°, having ir bands at 1770 and 1720 cm^{-1} and uv at 220 nm. Mass fragmentation data and signals in the pmr spectrum were in total agreement with those reported for inumakilactone B⁴. 4 was eluted with benzene-ethyl acetate (1:4) and crystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture, m.p. 276-78°. It formed a tetraacetate, m.p. 124-25°, as revealed in its pmr spectrum. Further, a signal corresponding to 1H at δ 4.85 (J 8 Hz) suggested it to be a glycoside. It was hydrolysed by HCl/acetic acid and the aglycone was identified as β -sitosterol and the sugar moiety as glucose. Hence, it was identified as the glucoside of β -sitosterol⁵.

The dried leaves (3 kg) were extracted with ethanol, and the concentrated extract was chromatographed on silica gel and the column eluted with benzene followed by increasingly polar mixtures of benzene-ethyl acetate. This resulted in the isolation of amentoflavone 7,7',4',4'''-tetramethyl ether (5), haveaflavone (6), amentoflavone 7',4'''-dimethyl ether (7), and amentoflavone (8). 5 was eluted from the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (19:1) and crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 273-74°. It was characterised as a flavonoid on the basis of colour reactions. Methylation and acetylation of 5 led to the formation of hexamethyl ether and tetramethoxydiacetate derivatives of amentoflavone respectively. Pmr spectra of its derivatives, mass spectral data and comparison of 5 with authentic sample confirmed its identity as amentoflavone 7,7',4',4'''-tetramethyl ether^{6,7}. 6 was crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture, m.p. 312°; λ_{max} 270 and 330 nm; ν_{max} 1670 cm^{-1} ; gave positive colour tests for flavonoids. It was identified as haveaflavone on the basis of pmr spectral data of the acetate of 6 and by comparison of the methyl ether of 6 with a sample of amentoflavone hexamethyl ether⁸. 7 was crystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture, m.p. 224°. Examination of the methylated product, m.p. 230°, and the pmr spectrum of its acetate led to its identification as amentoflavone 7',4'''-dimethyl ether⁹. 8 on methylation yielded amentoflavone hexamethyl ether, m.p. 227°, and on acetylation yielded hexacetate of amentoflavone, m.p. 240-42°. 8 was therefore identified as amentoflavone¹⁰.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (B.I.F. and S.A.K.) are grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of Fellow-